

Security Announcements

Getting Started Guide

General Concepts

Actors

Introduction to Actors

Actor lifecycle

Interaction Patterns

Fault Tolerance

Actor discovery

Routers

Stash

Behaviors as finite state machines

Example project

Coordinated Shutdown

Dispatchers

Mailboxes

Testing

Learning Akka Typed from Classic

Behaviors as finite state machines

For the Akka Classic documentation of this feature see [Classic FSM](#).

An actor can be used to model a Finite State Machine (FSM).

To demonstrate this, consider an actor which shall receive and queue messages while they arrive in a burst and send them on after the burst ended or a flush request is received.

This example demonstrates how to:

- Model states using different behaviors
- Model storing data at each state by representing the behavior as a method
- Implement state timeouts

The events the FSM can receive become the type of message the Actor can receive:

```
Scala Java
object Buncher {

  // FSM event becomes the type of the message Actor supports
  sealed trait Event
  final case class SetTarget(ref: ActorRef[Batch]) extends Event
  final case class Queue(obj: Any) extends Event
  case object Flush extends Event
  private case object Timeout extends Event
}
```

SetTarget is needed for starting it up, setting the destination for the Batches to be passed on; Queue will add to the internal queue while Flush will mark the end of a burst.

```
Scala Java
sealed trait Data
case object Uninitialized extends Data
final case class Todo(target: ActorRef[Batch], queue: immutable.Seq[Any]) extends Data

final case class Batch(obj: immutable.Seq[Any])
```

Each state becomes a distinct behavior and after processing a message the next state in the form of a Behavior is returned.

```
Scala Java
object Buncher {
  // states of the FSM represented as behaviors

  // initial state
  def apply(): Behavior[Event] = idle(Uninitialized)

  private def idle(data: Data): Behavior[Event] = Behaviors.receiveMessage[Event] { message: Event =>
    (message, data) match {
      case (SetTarget(ref), Uninitialized) =>
        idle(Todo(ref, Vector.empty))
      case (Queue(obj), t @ Todo(_, v)) =>
        active(t.copy(queue = v :+ obj))
      case _ =>
        Behaviors.unhandled
    }
  }

  private def active(data: Todo): Behavior[Event] =
    Behaviors.withTimers[Event] { timers =>
      // instead of FSM state timeout
      timers.startSingleTimer(Timeout, Timeout, 1.second)
      Behaviors.receiveMessagePartial {
        case Flush | Timeout =>
          data.target ! Batch(data.queue)
          idle(data.copy(queue = Vector.empty))
        case Queue(obj) =>
          active(data.copy(queue = data.queue :+ obj))
      }
    }
}
```

To set state timeouts use Behaviors.withTimers along with a startSingleTimer.

Example project

[FSM example project](#) is an example project that can be downloaded, and with instructions of how to run.

This project contains a Dining Hakkers sample illustrating how to model a Finite State Machine (FSM) with actors.

[← Stash](#)[Coordinated Shutdown →](#)

Found an error in this documentation? The source code for this page can be found [here](#). Please feel free to edit and contribute a pull request.

